

Studies on the Dependence of Optical Rotatory Power on Chemical Constitution. Part VIII. The Stereoisomeric *d*-, *l*-, *dl*-, *p*-Phenylene-, 1:4-Naphthylene-, *pp'*-Diphenylamine-, *pp'*-Diphenylmethane-bisimino-camphors ; *p*-Phenylene, *pp'*-Diphenylmethane-bisaminocamphors ; *p*-Diphenylamineiminocamphors and *p*-Diphenylamineaminocamphors, and their Derivatives.

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Up till the year 1920, Forster's *p*-phenylenebisimino-*d*-camphor (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 95, 942) was the classical instance, among carbon compounds, of a substance endowed with the highest rotatory power. The rotation constants of this compound were subsequently found to be exceeded by two substances prepared by one of us, namely, 1:4-naphthylenebisimino-*d*-camphor (*ibid.*, 1920, 117, 1599) and *pp'*-diphenylaminebisimino-*d*-camphor (*ibid.*, 1921, 119, 1975).

In the present communication, we have studied the imino-derivatives obtained from the condensation of the three stereoisomeric camphor-quinones (*d*-, *l*-, *dl*-) and the following aromatic amines: *p*-phenylene-diamine, 1:4-naphthylenediamine, *pp'*-diaminodiphenylamine, *pp'*-diaminodiphenylmethane and *p*-aminodiphenylamine.

The reduction of the imino to the amino-group in the molecule of this class of compounds is accompanied by a phenomenal depression in rotatory power, and this point has been emphasised in previous communications (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 980 ; 1921, 119, 1971). But in the case of compounds now under discussion it had not hitherto been realised owing to the difficulty of reducing these imino-derivatives. It may be recalled that Forster (*loc. cit.*, p. 955)

stated that "attempts to reduce this compound (*p*-phenylenebis-imino-*d*-camphor) have failed." It is now found that this failure was due to the rapid oxidation of the reduced compound. We have succeeded in reducing this compound as well as the *l*- and *dl*-isomerides and isolating the bisamino-compounds as the dihydrochlorides. The free bases are precipitated by the addition of water to the alcoholic solution of the hydrochlorides, and melt at 204° (*d*- and *l*-), and at 215°-218° with decomposition (*dl*-). The stereoisomeric *pp'*-diphenylmethanebisiminocamphors and *p*-iminocamphordiphenylamines have also been reduced to the corresponding amino-compounds, but it was not found possible to effect the isolation of 1:4-naphthylenebisaminocamphors and *pp'*-diphenylaminebisaminocamphors in a pure state owing to their being oxidised very rapidly by air as is described in the experimental portion. The depression in the rotatory power which accompanies the reduction of the azethenoid groups in the molecule of the three compounds tabulated below is illustrated by the following measurements in pyridine.

			$[\text{M}]_{\text{Hg green.}}^{35^\circ}$	Difference.
<i>p</i> -Phenylenebisiminocamphor	5945°	} 8044°
<i>p</i> -Phenylenebisaminocamphor	301°	
<i>pp'</i> -Diphenylmethanebisiminocamphor	6016°	} 5696°
<i>pp'</i> -Diphenylmethanebisaminocamphor	320°	
<i>p</i> -Iminocamphordiphenylamine	8818°	} 8648°
<i>p</i> -Aminocamphordiphenylamine	170°	

It will be seen that these phenomenal changes in rotatory power effected by the such slight changes in molecular weight of these compounds are unknown among optically active substances, and they also far surpass in magnitude any changes in rotatory power in similar types of compounds already known (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 980). It also illustrates the very great influence on rotatory power of conjugated double bonds when situated near the asymmetric centre.

The marked effect of unsaturation on rotatory power is brought out very clearly by counting the number of conjugated double bonds in the structural formulae of the six compounds shown in Table A, and comparing the specific rotatory power in different solvents. The rotatory power of compounds Nos. 1 to 5 increases as the number of conjugated double bonds in the molecule increases from 5 to 10. There is, however, no arithmetical proportion in these values. There is one marked exception to this rule in 1:4-naphthylenebisiminocamphor and *pp'*-bisiminocamphordiphenylamine. The former compound with nine conjugated double bonds has a higher specific rotatory power in pyridine than the latter which has ten. The molecular rotatory powers of the two compounds are, however, identical (Tables VI and VII). *pp'*-Diphenylenebisiminocamphor (Table A, No. 6) which has ten conjugated double bonds has higher rotatory power than *pp'*-diphenylmethanebisiminocamphor with five such bonds repeated twice, the conjugation being broken at the methane carbon atom, but it is less than that for the other four compounds (Nos. 2 to 5) with 7, 8, 9 and 10 such bonds respectively. This once more illustrates the effect of the optimum association of azethenoid groups, conjugated linkings and benzene rings within a given molecular compass. The narrower the molecular compass containing a given number of conjugated linkings, the greater is the rotation.

TABLE A.

Structural formula.	Name of conjugated double bonds.	[α] _D ^{25°}					
		Benzene (9.26)†	Chloro- form (5.2)	Pyridine (12.4)	Acetone (31.5)	EtOH (25.8)	MeOH (31.2)
1. C_8H_{14}	5	905.3°	899.2°	921.5°	811.0°	880.6°	807.8°
2. C_8H_{14}	7	1567	1527	1562.6	1384.5	1844	1258
3. C_8H_{14}	8	1607	1608.5	2026	1667	2141	1698

<p>4. </p>	9	1902	1776	2908	2522	2621	2059
<p>5. </p>	10	2533	2882	2667	2629	2702	2517
<p>6* </p>	10	...	1140	1046

* Singh, Singh and Lal, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 419, 1974.

‡ Dielectric constant is given within brackets below the names of the solvents.

p-Iminocamphordiphenylamine has been assigned the structure represented by formula No. 3 (Table A), but its mode of formation leads to the following conventional formula,

in which the conjugation is broken at the second benzene ring at its junction with the nitrogen atom of the amino-group, and shown by dotted line in the formula. This structure in which the conjugation between the two benzene rings is broken cannot be reconciled with its high rotatory power. But by depicting the quinonoid arrangement as in formula No. 3 (Table A), the conjugation in the molecule becomes continuous. The same explanation has already been advanced in the case of *pp'*-bisiminocamphordiphenylamine (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 1971). The double symmetric quinonoid arrangement as represented in formula No. 5 (Table A) maintains an unbroken chain of conjugated double bonds which is not the case with the non-quinonoid arrangement, and not only does it explain the highest rotatory power which this compound possesses, but it also explains the fluorescence which this substance exhibits in solution (*loc. cit.*).

The acetyl derivatives of *p*-iminocamphordiphenylamine and *pp'*-bisiminocamphordiphenylamine have rotatory power which is of the same order as that of *pp'*-bisiminocamphordiphenylmethane. This suggests that the structure of the acetyl derivatives is, unlike the parent compounds, to be represented by formulae in which the conjugation is broken (as shown by dotted lines), as it, undoubtedly, is in *pp'*-bisiminocamphordiphenylmethane.

p-Phenylenebisaminocamphor is of interest on account of the reversal of sign of the rotatory power which takes place when the free base is converted into its acetyl derivative. The rotatory power of the optically active acetyl derivatives is opposite in sign in pyridine but not in chloroform (Table III). A reversal of sign on salt formation has been observed previously in solutions of the salts of brucine and coniine (Hilditch, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 700), and of nicotine (Nasini and Pezzolato, *Gazzetta*, 1893, 23, 43; Lowry and Lloyd, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, p. 1772), and a similar reversal occurs when tetrahydroquinaldine, $[\alpha]_D = +230^\circ$ is converted into its benzoyl derivative, $[\alpha]_D = -61.2^\circ$ (Pope and Read, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 2206), or into other derivatives of a similar type (Pope and Winmill, *ibid.*, 1912, 101, 2309). A possible explanation of this reversal of the sign of rotatory power in benzoyltetrahydroquinaldine and acetyl-*p*-phenylenebisaminocamphor may be given by the postulation of a "dative bond" (Menzies, *Nature*, 1928, 121, 457) between the acyl oxygen and the hydrogen atom attached to the asymmetric carbon atom (C) in the following formulae.

Benzoyltetrahydroquinaldine.

Acetyl-*p*-phenylenebisaminocamphor.

The reversal of sign of the rotatory power in these compounds may thus be associated with the saturation of a lone pair of electrons on the acyl oxygen. A similar explanation in the case of nicotine and its salts has been offered by Lowry and Lloyd (*loc. cit.*)

The Influence of Solvent on the Rotatory Power.—The solvents employed in this investigation in the decreasing order of their dielectric constants are methyl alcohol > ethyl alcohol > acetone > pyridine > chloroform > benzene. A reference to the tables of rotatory power (I to XII) will show that the sequence of solvents in order of decreasing (or increasing) rotatory power is quite different from that of their dielectric constants, and does not run strictly parallel with them even in one instance. In *p*-phenylenebisaminocamphor the sequence is obeyed except that pyridine and chloroform exhibit an

inverted relationship. In about fifty per cent. cases investigated, the order of rotatory power for the oxygen containing solvents is acetone > ethyl alcohol > methyl alcohol (see Tables I, II, VI, IX, and XII) which is the same as that of their dielectric constants but in a reverse order. This regularity has already been noticed with the derivatives of *d*-camphorimide and *d*-camphoramic acid (Singh and Puri, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 129, 504). The solvent pyridine is, however, remarkable in one respect. The rotatory power of the mono- or bis-iminocamphor derivatives is highest in this solvent, whereas it becomes lowest when these compounds are converted into the mono- or bisaminocamphor derivatives respectively.

The Influence of Chemical Constitution on Rotatory Dispersion.—Biot classified rotatory dispersions in two groups according as they did, or did not, obey the law of inverse squares $[\alpha] = k/\lambda^2$. The work of Lowry and his school has shown that this law is never disobeyed exactly, although some substances such as sodium tartrate (Lowry and Austin, *Phil. Trans.*, 1922 A, 222, 249) and octyl oxalate (Lowry and Richards, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 1593) obey it very nearly. Lowry (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1914, 10, 96) has classified rotatory dispersions as "simple" and "complex" according as they can or cannot be expressed by the equation $[\alpha] = k/(\lambda_2 - \lambda_0^2)$. This equation which differs from Biot's equation only by the addition of λ_0^2 was deduced by Drude in 1898 for rotatory dispersion in transparent media; it does not, therefore, apply to the absorbent media studied by Cotton (*Compt. rend.*, 1895, 120, 949, 1044; *Ann. chim. Phys.*, 1896, vii, 8, 347) where anomalies are observed on passing through the region of absorption. The "simple" formula is valid for a large number of secondary alcohols containing one asymmetric carbon atom (Lowry and Dickson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 103, 1067; Lowry and Richard, *loc. cit.*). Among numerous other substances which obey the "simple" dispersion law are sucrose, camphorquinone (Lowry and Richards, *ibid*, 1924, 125, 2511), and nicotine (Lowry and Singh, *Compt. rend.*, 1925, 181, 909; Lowry and Lloyd, *loc. cit.*).

The rotatory dispersion of camphor and most of its derivatives cannot be expressed by the one-term equation of Drude. It is therefore not "simple" but "complex". In nearly every case however, it can be expressed by using two terms of Drude's equation (Lowry and Cutter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 604), although the dispersions are sometimes normal as in the case of camphor itself, and

sometimes anomalous as in the case of α' -bromocamphor the dispersion curve of which is unique as it shows all the three characteristic anomalies simultaneously, namely, an inflexion, a maximum and a reversal of sign.

The substances investigated in the present paper show all the three types of rotatory dispersion, namely "simple," "complex" and "anomalous". The graphical method of analysis which consists in plotting $1/\alpha$ against λ^2 was applied in every case. Those cases in which straight lines were not obtained were at once shown to conform to complex or anomalous rotatory dispersion. In a few cases straight lines were obtained which pointed that they may represent simple rotatory dispersion. These were then analysed by the more exact numerical method, which consists in working out a dispersion formula based on the one-term equation of Drude, $[\alpha] = k/(\lambda^2 - \lambda_0^2)$ and then seeing whether the observed and calculated rotations show *systematic* errors, or *casual* errors. As our observations were made with three or four wave-lengths only, no attempt was made to find a rotatory dispersion formula involving two-terms of Drude's equation. The results of our analysis in the above mentioned way have shown that the substances which exhibit simple rotatory dispersion are the acetyl derivatives of *pp'*-diphenylaminebisiminocamphors (Table VI), *p*-diphenylamineaminocamphors (Table IX) in all the solvents, and diacetyl derivatives of *p*-diphenylamineaminocamphors in all the solvents except pyridine (Table X), in which the differences in the observed and calculated values of rotatory power are greater than the experimental errors. In the same category may be perhaps, included *pp'*-diphenylmethanebisiminocamphors in acetone and methyl alcohol (Table XI) and their reduction products namely, *pp'*-diphenylmethanebisaminocamphors in acetone, methyl alcohol and ethyl alcohol (Table XII). The monoacetyl derivatives of *p*-phenylenebisaminocamphors show anomalous dispersion in pyridine (Table III); the dispersion curves cut the axis of zero rotation at some wave-length lying between Hg_{violet} and Hg_{green} , and thus exhibit one of the three characteristic anomalies, namely, reversal of sign of rotatory power. In chloroform solution it however, shows complex rotatory dispersion, to which type also the remaining substances conform.

It will be further observed that there is no connection between the number of asymmetric centres in a molecule and the type of rotatory dispersion which it exhibits. Camphorquinone and camphor

contain two asymmetric carbon atoms but the rotatory dispersion of the former compound is "simple", whereas that of the latter "complex" (*loc. cit.*). The optically active *pp'*-diphenylaminebisiminocamphors and their acetyl derivatives have four asymmetric carbon atoms but the rotatory dispersion of the former compound is "complex", whereas that of the latter "simple". The *pp'*-diphenylmethanebisaminocamphors have six asymmetric carbon atoms, but their rotatory dispersion is "simple" in acetone, methyl alcohol and ethyl alcohol, and "complex" in chloroform, benzene, and pyridine. The monoacetyl derivatives of *p*-phenylenebisaminocamphors contain also six asymmetric carbon atoms, but the rotatory dispersion is "complex" in chloroform, and anomalous in pyridine.

The last examples cited also show that the type of rotatory dispersion of a molecule is dependent on the nature of the solvent in which it is dissolved. The dispersion constant λ^2_0 , in the one term Drude's equation enables the value of λ_0 , the wave-length of the absorption band in the ultra-violet, to be calculated. This value varies from about 3500 to 3700 A. U. for the acetyl derivatives of the optically active *pp'*-diphenylaminebisiminocamphors in different solvents. This indirect determination of the wave-length of the ultra-violet absorption band (head) should be compared with that obtained by direct measurement. It could thus be used in testing the validity of the application of Drude's equation for rotatory dispersion. It is hoped to make this comparison in a later communication. The values of λ_0 for other substance showing "simple" rotatory dispersion are given in the tables of rotations.

The Physical Identity of Enantiomers.—Since the discovery of molecular asymmetry by Pasteur, and later by Van't Hoff and Le Bel, it has always been *assumed* that apart from the sign of rotation, the physical properties of the dextro- and laevo-enantiomers are identical, whereas these properties are different for racemic forms.

About four years ago, we commenced the present investigation, which had, as one of its objects, the experimental confirmation (or otherwise) of the above mentioned assumption, namely, the equality in the numerical value of the rotatory power of the opposite active forms. The compounds described in this paper possess very high rotatory power; they, therefore, lend themselves remarkably well for this comparison. A reference to Tables I to XII will show that the differences in the values of rotatory power of the dextro- and

laevo-forms are very small indeed, and are well within the experimental errors. So far as these compounds are concerned, it may be safely concluded that the assumption of the equality of rotatory power of enantiomers is not disproved. On the other hand it may be claimed that the results of the experiments now described fully support it.

The melting points of the racemic forms of the substances are different from those of the opposite active forms. Where the melting point of the inactive form is higher than that of the active, there can be no doubt that the inactive form is, in the solid state, a true racemate. But where the racemic form has lower melting point, further experiments are required to settle whether it is a true compound, or a mixture of equal proportions of the two enantiomers. If the melting point of the racemic form can be lowered by the addition of the optically active form, there can be no doubt that the racemic form is not a mixture, but a true racemate. The melting points of the racemic forms of 1:4-naphthylenebisiminocamphor and *pp'*-diphenylmethanebisiminocamphor are depressed by 2–3° on the addition of about 10 per cent. of their dextro-isomerides, which points them to be true racemates. The case is quite different with the racemic form of *p*-phenylenebisiminocamphor, as its melting point is continuously raised by the addition of gradually increasing quantities of the *d*-isomeride (*vide* Experimental). This shows that the racemic form of this substance is a mixture.

EXPERIMENTAL.

p-Phenylenebisimino-*d*-camphor (Formula 2, Table A).

This substance was prepared in a slightly different way from that of Forster's (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 95, 942) with improved yield. *d*-Camphorquinone (2 mols.), *p*-phenylenediamine hydrochloride (1 mol.) and excess of freshly fused sodium acetate were heated on a water-bath for 8 hours. The mass was extracted with hot alcohol, and precipitated with water. It was crystallised out of alcohol, as golden yellow needles melting at 259°-280°, (yield, 60%). The substance is freely soluble in chloroform, benzene and pyridine; less readily in acetone, less so in ethyl alcohol and methyl alcohol; slightly soluble in ether and insoluble in water. (Found: N, 7.05; $C_{26}H_{32}O_2N_2$ requires N, 6.93 per cent.). The order of rotatory power

in different solvents (see Table I) is as below:—Benzene > pyridine > chloroform > acetone > ethyl alcohol > methyl alcohol. *p*-Phenylenebisimino-*l*-camphor was obtained from *l*-camphorquinone in the same way. It had the same melting point, solubility, and order of rotatory power (see Table I) as the *d*-isomeride. (Found: C, 77·22; H, 8·15. C₂₆H₃₂O₂N₂ requires C, 77·23; H, 7·92 per cent).

p-Phenylenebisimino-*dl*-camphor was prepared from *dl*-camphorquinone in the same way as the corresponding *d*- and *l*-compounds, and crystallises as yellow needles melting at 252-253°. (Found: N, 7·15. C₂₆H₃₂O₂N₂ requires N, 6·93 per cent.). The following table of mixed melting points of *d*- and *dl*-isomerides shows that the substance is probably a racemic mixture and not a racemic compound.

Proportion of <i>dl</i> -isomeride.	Proportion of <i>d</i> -isomeride.	M.p.
100%	Nil	252°-53°
90	10%	253°-54°
50	50	253°-54°
15	85	254°-55°
5	95	257°-56°
Nil	100	259°-60°

A mixture of equal quantities of *d*- and *l*-isomerides melts at 252-53°.

p-Phenylenebisamino-*d*-camphor Dihydrochloride.

p-Phenylenebisimino-*d*-camphor (1 g.) dissolved in 100 c.c. of benzene was shaken with 100 c.c. of 10 per cent. caustic potash solution in presence of zinc dust (5 g.) continuously until the benzene layer was colourless (10 to 12 hours). It was filtered off free from zinc dust, the benzene layer separated and washed with water till free from alkali. The solution turned pink immediately on exposure. The operations were completed as quickly as possible as the substance is liable to be oxidised rapidly in solution. Dry hydrochloric

acid gas was then passed through the benzene solution when a gelatinous mass (pinkish) was precipitated: this was filtered off, washed with benzene and dried (yield, 85 to 90 per cent.).

It has no sharp melting point; it darkens from 217° melting completely at 225°. It is easily soluble in ethyl alcohol but the free base is liberated from the salt when it is shaken with water. (Found: Cl, 14.50. $C_{26}H_{38}O_2N_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 14.76 per cent.).

p-Phenylenebisamino-d-camphor.—The dried hydrochloride was dissolved in alcohol (the solution turning violet) and precipitated with water. It was crystallised from hot alcohol as white prisms melting at 204°. The yield was 65-70 per cent.

It is very readily soluble in pyridine, chloroform, benzene and acetone; less so in ethyl alcohol and methyl alcohol, slightly soluble in ether and insoluble in water. (Found: C, 76.81; H, 8.85. $C_{26}H_{38}O_2N_2$ requires C, 76.47; H, 8.82 per cent.).

The order of rotatory power in solvents (see Table II) is as below: Chloroform > benzene > acetone > ethyl alcohol > methyl alcohol > pyridine. *p-Phenylenebisamino-l-camphor dihydrochloride* was prepared in the same way as the corresponding dextro-isomeride and has similar properties. (Found: Cl, 14.69. $C_{26}H_{38}N_2O_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 14.76 per cent.). *p-Phenylenebisamino-l-camphor* was prepared in the same way as the corresponding dextro-compound and has the same melting point and solubility. (Found: C, 76.26; H, 9.10. $C_{26}H_{38}N_2O_2$ requires C, 76.47; H, 8.82 per cent.).

The values of rotatory power of the *l*-isomeride are identical with those of the *d*-compound within experimental error (see Table II).

p-Phenylenebisamino-dl-camphor dihydrochloride was prepared in the same way as the corresponding *d*- and *l*-isomerides. (Found: Cl, 14.63. $C_{26}H_{38}O_2N_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 14.76 per cent.).

p-Phenylenebisamino-dl-camphor was prepared in the same way as the corresponding dextro- and laevo-compounds but unlike them it has no sharp melting point. It begins to turn yellow from 198°, completely yellow at 210°, blackening begins from 215°, melting completely at 220°. It is soluble in benzene and chloroform; less so in ethyl alcohol and methyl alcohol and sparingly soluble in ether. (Found: C, 76.40; H, 9.12. $C_{26}H_{38}O_2N_2$ requires C, 76.47; H, 8.82 per cent.).

Monoacetyl Derivative of p-Phenylenebisamino-d-camphor.—*p*-Phenylenebisamino-*d*-camphor (1 g.) was heated with acetic anhydride (1.2 g.) at 195-200° for 20-25 minutes and poured into water while still hot when it solidified. It was crystallised out of 70 per cent. alcohol as white silky needles (yield, 50%). It has no sharp melting point; darkening from 245°, it shows signs of melting at 250° and completely melts at 253-54°. It is readily soluble in chloroform and pyridine, less so in benzene and acetone; sparingly soluble in alcohol and insoluble in water. (Found: C, 74.59; H, 8.78. $C_{28}H_{38}O_3N_2$ requires C, 74.66; H, 8.44 per cent.). Found: acetyl (hydrolysis method)=8.49; acetyl (Perkin's method)=9.78. $C_{28}H_{38}O_3N_2$ (monoacetyl) requires acetyl, 9.50 per cent.).

The rotatory power was determined in chloroform and pyridine only (see Table III) as the solubility in other solvents was too small. The *l*-isomeride was prepared in the same way and has similar properties. (Found: C, 74.54; H, 8.68. $C_{28}H_{38}O_3N_2$ requires C, 74.66; H, 8.44 per cent.).

The sign of rotatory power for the *d*- and *l*-isomerides is opposite in pyridine solution for Hg_{green} , Hg_{yellow} and Na_D lines but same for Hg_{violet} (see Table III).

The *monoacetyl* derivative of *p*-phenylenebisamino-*dl*-camphor was prepared and crystallised in the same way as the corresponding optically active isomerides and has similar solubility but unlike them, melts at 192-93° (white crystals). (Found: C, 74.50; H, 8.66. $C_{28}H_{38}O_3N_2$ requires C, 74.66; H, 8.44 per cent.).

1:4-Naphthylenebisimino-*d*-camphor (Formula 3, Table A).

It was prepared according to the method given by one of us (Singh and Singh, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 1601) and obtained as red plates melting at 220-22°. It is freely soluble in organic media excepting ether which dissolves the substance only sparingly. (Found: C, 79.16; H, 7.75. $C_{30}H_{34}O_2N_2$ requires C, 79.29; H, 7.49 per cent.).

The substance is thus identical with that already described (*loc. cit.*) except that the melting point recorded there is 8° higher, which is obviously a misprint. The order of rotatory power in solvents (see Table IV) is as follows: Pyridine > ethyl alcohol > acetone > methyl alcohol > benzene > chloroform. 1:4-Naphthylenebisimino-*l*-camphor was prepared in the same way as the corresponding *d*-isomeride and has the same melting point and solubility. (Found:

C, 79.10; H, 7.39. $C_{30}H_{34}O_2N_2$ requires C, 79.29; H, 7.49 per cent.).

The rotatory power is identical with that of the *d*-isomeride within experimental error (see Table IV).

1:4-Naphthylenebisimino-*dl*-camphor was prepared in a similar way as the corresponding *d*- and *l*-compounds and had similar solubility but melts at 213°-14° (red plates). (Found: C, 78.89; H, 7.51. $C_{30}H_{34}O_2N_2$ requires C, 79.29; H, 7.49 per cent.).

All attempts to isolate the reduced product of 1:4-naphthylenebisiminocamphor have failed for although the ethereal solution of the substance becomes colourless when shaken with 10 per cent. potassium hydroxide solution and zinc dust, it turned red immediately on exposure to air and a substance of varying composition and melting point could only be isolated. The rapid change could not be checked even when all the operations such as filtration, evaporation, etc., were conducted in an inert atmosphere of hydrogen or carbon dioxide. The hydrochloride as formed by passing dry hydrochloric acid gas through the reduced ethereal solution had also a varying composition (always showing a higher chlorine content); the free base liberated by the addition of ammonia was very unstable changing from grey to brown very rapidly (specially in solution) and when it was tried to crystallise out of alcohol, a red substance (m.p. 180°-85°) was obtained.

pp'-Diphenylaminebisimino-*d*-camphor (Formula 5, Table A).

This substance was prepared according to the method given by one of us (Singh, Singh and Lal, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 1975) with improved yield and formed greenish-yellow prisms melting at 212°-13° (yield, 60 per cent.).

It is freely soluble in organic media excepting ether which dissolves it only sparingly. (Found: C, 77.48; H, 7.70. $C_{32}H_{37}O_2N_3$ requires C, 77.58; H, 7.47 per cent.).

The order of rotatory power in different solvents (see Table V) is: ethyl alcohol > pyridine > acetone > benzene, > methyl alcohol > chloroform. The *l*-isomeride was prepared in a similar way from *l*-camphorquinone and has the same melting point and solubility in different organic media. (Found: C, 77.51; H, 7.73. $C_{32}H_{37}O_2N_3$ requires C, 77.58; H, 7.47 per cent.).

The rotatory power is identical with that of the *d*-isomeride (Table V).

pp'-Diphenylaminebisimino-*dl*-camphor was prepared and crystallised in the same way as the corresponding optically active isomerides (much more tarry matter separated in this case which was washed off with a little ether, the last traces being removed by boiling the alcoholic solution with a trace of animal charcoal). It crystallised as scarlet red plates melting at 144°-45°. (Found: N, 8.58. $C_{32}H_{37}O_2N_3$ requires N, 8.49 per cent.).

The acetyl derivative of *pp'*-diphenylaminebisimino-*d*-camphor was prepared by heating *pp'*-diphenylaminebisimino-*d*-camphor (1 g.) with acetic anhydride (2 g.) at 170-180° for an hour, and obtained as greenish-yellow plates melting at 227° (yield, 0.6 g.). It is readily soluble in chloroform, benzene, acetone, and pyridine; less so in ethyl alcohol and methyl alcohol and insoluble in water. (Found: C, 76.18; H, 7.52. $C_{34}H_{39}O_3N_3$ requires C, 75.98; and H, 7.26 per cent.). The order of rotatory power (Table VI) is as below: benzene > pyridine > chloroform > acetone > ethyl alcohol > methyl alcohol. Attempts to prepare a methyl derivative of *pp'*-diphenylaminebisimino-*d*-camphor have failed.

The corresponding *l*-isomeride was prepared in a similar way *pp'*-diphenylaminebisimino-*l*-camphor and has the same melting point and solubility in different organic media. (Found: C, 75.86; H, 7.55. $C_{34}H_{39}O_3N_3$ requires C, 75.98; H, 7.26 per cent.). The rotatory power is identical with the dextro-isomeride in all solvents (Table VI).

pp'-Diphenylaminebisimino-*dl*-camphor could not be acetylated.

p-Imino-*d*-camphordiphenylamine (Formula B, Table A).

d-Camphorquinone (1 mol.) was heated with *p*-aminodiphenylamine hydrochloride (1 mol.) with fused sodium acetate at about 75° for 4-5 hours. The mass was extracted with alcohol and precipitated with water. The precipitate crystallised as yellowish-green needles melting at 134°-35° (yield, 70-80%). It is readily soluble in different organic media. (Found: C, 79.44; H, 7.46. $C_{22}H_{24}ON_2$ requires C, 79.52; H, 7.25 per cent.).

The order of rotatory power (see Table VII) is as below: ethyl alcohol > pyridine > methyl alcohol > chloroform > acetone > benzene.

p-Imino-*l*-camphordiphenylamine was prepared in a similar way as the corresponding dextro-isomeride and has the same melting point and similar solubility. (Found: C, 79.38; H, 7.54.

$C_{22}H_{24}ON_2$ requires C, 79.52; H, 7.23 per cent.). The rotatory power in different solvents is identical in numerical value with that of the *d*-isomeride (see Table VII).

p-Imino-*d*-camphordiphenylamine was prepared in the same way as the corresponding *d*- and *l*-compounds and crystallised as yellowish-orange shining plates melting at 144°-45°. It is readily soluble in different organic media. (Found: C, 79.52; H, 7.48. $C_{22}H_{24}ON_2$ requires C, 79.52; H, 7.23 per cent.).

The *acetyl* derivative of *p*-imino-*d*-camphordiphenylamine was prepared by heating *p*-imino-*d*-camphordiphenylamine with acetic anhydride at 165°-170° for an hour, and was obtained as greenish-yellow plates melting at 163°-64° (yield, 60-65%). It is readily soluble in chloroform, benzene; less so in ethyl alcohol and methyl alcohol. (Found: C, 76.88; H, 7.22. $C_{24}H_{26}O_2N_2$ requires C, 77.00; H, 6.95 per cent.). The order of rotatory power in different solvents (Table VIII) is—

benzene > pyridine > chloroform > ethyl alcohol, acetone > methyl alcohol. The *l*-isomeride was prepared in a similar way from *p*-imino-*l*-camphordiphenylamine and has the same melting point and solubility. (Found: C, 76.86; H, 7.27. $C_{24}H_{26}O_2N_2$ requires C, 77.00; H, 6.95 per cent.). The numerical value of the rotatory power in different solvents is identical with that of the *d*-compound (Table VIII).

The *acetyl* derivative of *p*-imino-*dl*-camphordiphenylamine was prepared in the same way as the corresponding dextro- and laevo-isomerides and crystallised as light green plates melting at 153°-54°. It is readily soluble in different organic media. (Found: C, 76.91; H, 7.26. $C_{24}H_{26}O_2N_2$ requires C, 77.00; H, 6.95 per cent.).

Attempts to prepare a methyl derivative of *p*-imino-*d*-camphordiphenylamine have failed.

p-Amino-*d*-camphordiphenylamine,

was prepared in the usual way, by the reduction of *p*-imino-*d*-camphordiphenylamine (in ether solution) with 10 per cent. potassium hydroxide solution in presence of zinc dust, and was obtained as shining white plates melting at 121°-22°. It is readily soluble

in different organic media. (Found: C, 78.96; H, 8.10. $C_{22}H_{26}ON_2$ requires C, 79.05; H, 7.79 per cent.). The order of rotatory power in different solvents (see Table IX) is as follows:

benzene > chloroform > acetone > ethyl alcohol > methyl alcohol > pyridine.

p-Amino-*l*-camphordiphenylamine was prepared in a similar way as the corresponding *d*-isomeride and has the same melting point and solubility. (Found: C, 78.76; H, 7.99. $C_{22}H_{26}ON_2$ requires C, 79.05; H, 7.79 per cent.).

The rotatory power in different solvents is identical with that of the *d*-isomeride (see Table IX).

p-Amino-*dl*-camphordiphenylamine was prepared in the same way as the other two isomerides and crystallised as shining plates (white) melting at 98-94°. It is readily soluble in different organic media. (Found: C, 78.56; H, 8.19. $C_{22}H_{26}ON_2$ requires C, 79.05; H, 7.79 per cent.).

The *diacetyl* derivative of *p*-amino-*d*-camphordiphenylamine was prepared by heating *p*-amino-*d*-camphordiphenylamine (1 g.) with acetic anhydride (3 g.) at 140-150° for 20 minutes, and obtained as white prisms melting at 190-91° (yield, 0.6 g.). (Found: C, 74.49; H, 7.52. $C_{26}H_{30}O_3N_2$ requires C, 74.64; H, 7.18 per cent.).

The order of rotatory power in four solvents (see Table X) is benzene > chloroform > acetone > pyridine.

The rotatory power in ethyl alcohol and methyl alcohol was not determined owing to its small solubility in these solvents. The *l*-isomeride was prepared in a similar way from *p*-amino-*l*-camphordiphenylamine and has the same melting point and solubility. (Found: C, 74.63; H, 7.78. $C_{26}H_{30}O_3N_2$ requires C, 74.64; H, 7.18 per cent.).

The rotatory power is identical in numerical value with that of the *d*-isomeride (see Table X).

The *monoacetyl* derivative of *p*-amino-*d*-camphordiphenylamine was prepared by heating *p*-amino-*dl*-camphordiphenylamine with acetic anhydride at 160-170° for 30 minutes, and obtained as light white microscopic crystals melting at 175°-76°. It is readily soluble in chloroform, benzene, pyridine and acetone; less readily in ethyl alcohol and methyl alcohol. (Found: C, 76.34; H, 7.94. $C_{24}H_{28}O_2N_2$ requires C, 76.60; H, 7.44 per cent.).

It is rather curious that the racemic compound forms only a monoacetyl derivative and the corresponding *d*- and *l*-compounds give diacetyl derivatives.

pp'-Diphenylmethanebisimino-*d*-camphor (Formula 1, Table A).

d-Camphorquinone (2 mols.) was heated on the water-bath with *pp'*-diaminodiphenylmethane (1 mol.) in presence of fused sodium sulphate for 7 to 8 hours. The mass was extracted with alcohol and precipitated with water. It was crystallised out of dilute alcohol as yellow prisms melting at 203-204° (yield, 60 per cent.). It is readily soluble in alcohol, chloroform, benzene, acetone and pyridine; less readily in ether and insoluble in water. (Found: C, 79.97; H, 7.90. $C_{33}H_{38}O_2N_2$ requires C, 80.16; H, 7.69 per cent.).

The order of rotatory power in different solvents (Table XI) is pyridine > benzene > chloroform > ethyl alcohol > acetone > methyl alcohol. The *l*-isomeride was prepared in a similar way and has the same melting point and solubility. (Found: C, 80.02; H, 7.99. $C_{33}H_{38}O_2N_2$ requires C, 80.16; H, 7.69 per cent.).

The magnitude of the rotatory power is identical with that of the *d*-compound (Table XI).

pp'-Diphenylmethanebisimino-*dl*-camphor was prepared in a similar way as the corresponding *d*- and *l*-compounds and crystallised as yellow prisms melting at 200-201°. (Found: C, 79.86; H, 7.82. $C_{33}H_{38}O_2N_2$ requires C, 80.16; H, 7.82 per cent.).

pp'-Diphenylmethanebisamino-*d*-camphor.

was prepared in the usual way by the reduction of *pp'*-diphenylmethanebisimino-*d*-camphor with 10 per cent. potassium hydroxide solution in presence of zinc dust, and was obtained as light cream-coloured crystals (probably prisms) melting at 182° (yield, 50 per cent.). It is readily soluble in chloroform, benzene, pyridine, ether and acetone; less so in ethyl alcohol, sparingly soluble in methyl alcohol and insoluble in water. (Found: C, 78.89; H, 8.54. $C_{33}H_{42}O_2N_2$ requires C, 79.51; H, 8.44 per cent.).

The order of rotatory power in different solvents (Table XII) is benzene > chloroform > acetone > ethyl alcohol > methyl alcohol > pyridine.

The *l*-isomeride was prepared in a similar way from *pp'*-diphenylmethanebisimino-*l*-camphor and has the same melting point and

solubility. (Found: C, 79.16; H, 8.76. $C_{33}H_{42}O_2N_2$ requires C, 79.51; H, 8.44 per cent.).

The value of the rotatory power in different solvents is identical with that of the *d*-compound (Table XII).

pp'-Diphenylmethanebisamino-*dl*-camphor was prepared in a similar way as the two optically active isomerides and crystallised as light cream-coloured crystals melting at 164°-65°. (Found: C, 79.60; H, 8.59. $C_{33}H_{42}O_2N_2$ requires C, 79.51; H, 8.44 per cent.).

Attempts to isolate the acetyl derivative of *pp'*-diphenylmethanebisamino-*d*-camphor have failed.

The rotatory power determinations recorded in Tables I to XII, were made in a 2 dcm. jacketed tube and the temperature was maintained at 35° throughout these observations. Hg_{vic} , Hg_{gr} , Hg_{yel} and Na_D refer to the violet mercury line 4358, the green mercury line 5461, the yellow mercury line 5780, and the yellow sodium line 5893 respectively. In the case of compounds, which show simple rotatory dispersion, the value of λ_0 has been calculated from the dispersion formula, and is expressed as μ or 10^{-4} cm.

TABLE I.

p-Phenylenebisaminocamphor.

Solvent.	Concentration: g./100 c.c.	Dextro, laevo, or mean.	[M]		
			Na_D	Hg_{yel}	Hg_{gr}
Benzene	0.0784	<i>d</i>	+6331°	+6569°	+8476°
	0.0696	<i>l</i>	-6387	-6585	-8472
		Mean	6359	6577	8474
Pyridine	0.0736	<i>d</i>	+6313	+6503	+8345
	0.0792	<i>l</i>	-6270	-6476	-8338
		Mean	62.2	6490	8342
Chloroform	0.0724	<i>d</i>	+6169	+6387	+8173
	0.0716	<i>l</i>	-6152	-6404	-8212
		Mean	610	6395	8193
Acetone	0.0780	<i>d</i>	+5593	+5680	+7171
	0.0756	<i>l</i>	-5656	-5712	-7191
		Mean	5624	5696	7181
Ethyl alcohol	0.0740	<i>d</i>	+5430	+5543	+7150
	0.0840	<i>l</i>	-5410	-5531	-7118
		Mean	5420	5537	7134
Methyl alcohol	0.0704	<i>d</i>	+5082	+5224	+6690
	0.0700	<i>l</i>	-5078	-5224	-6698
		Mean	5080	5224	6694

TABLE II.

p-Phenylenebisaminocamphor.

Solvent.	Concentration : g./100 c.c.	Dextro, laevo, or mean.	[M]		
			N _{sD}	Hg _{yel.}	Hg _{gr.}
Chloroform	0.4090	<i>d</i>	+470.0*	+534.9*	+610.0*
	0.4194	<i>l</i>	-488.1	-518.9	-604.6
		Mean	469.05	525.0	607.3
Benzene	0.4094	<i>d</i>	+439.4	+499.9	574.2
	0.4168	<i>l</i>	-445.4	-494.4	-577.7
		Mean	442.4	497.1	575.9
Acetone	0.4196	<i>d</i>	+428.9	+481.5	+550.8
	0.4184	<i>l</i>	-419.4	-477.8	-548.2
		Mean	423.1	479.6	548.5
Ethyl alcohol	0.1660	<i>d</i>	+331.4	+417.9	+504.0
	0.1700	<i>l</i>	-324.1	-418.0	-492.0
		Mean	327.7	412.9	498.0
Methyl alcohol	0.1688	<i>d</i>	+302.1	+326.3	+398.8
	0.1708	<i>l</i>	-298.5	-334.5	-406.2
		Mean	300.3	330.4	402.5
Pyridine	0.4136	<i>d</i>	+236.7	+256.5	+300.9
	0.4060	<i>l</i>	-243.8	-248.3	-293.6
		Mean	240.2	252.4	297.2

Concentration of the substance in ethyl alcohol and methyl alcohol was not same as in other solvents, the substance being not so readily soluble in them.

TABLE III.

Monoacetyl Derivative of p-Phenylenebisaminocamphor.

Solvent.	Concentration : g./100 c.c.	Dextro, laevo, or mean.	[M]			
			N _{sD}	Hg _{yel.}	Hg _{gr.}	Hg _{vis.}
Chloroform	0.4352	<i>d</i>	+124.06*	+180.47*	+201.64*	...
	0.4444	<i>l</i>	-128.58	-161.95	-202.59	...
		Mean	125.32	161.21	202.12	...
Pyridine	0.4148	<i>d</i>	-108.45	-86.85	-59.87	+54.22*
	0.4164	<i>l</i>	+97.34	+81.04	+59.4	-48.6
		Mean	102.85	83.95	59.54	51.41

The substance was difficultly soluble in other solvents ; hence readings could not be taken in them.

TABLE IV.

1:4-Naphthylenebisiminocamphor.

Solvent.	Concentration g./100 c.c.	Dextro, laevo or mean.	[M]	
			Na _D	Hg _{yel.}
Pyridine	0.0141	<i>d</i>	+13200*	+14170*
	0.0155	<i>l</i>	-13320	-14060
		Mean	13230	14115
Ethyl alcohol	0.0145	<i>d</i>	+11899	+12528
	0.0150	<i>l</i>	-11980	-12560
		Mean	11930	12543
Acetone	0.0155	<i>d</i>	+10540	+11570
	0.0149	<i>l</i>	-10520	-11430
		Mean	10530	11500
Methyl alcohol	0.0153	<i>d</i>	+9348	+10390
	0.0148	<i>l</i>	-9365	-10280
		Mean	9352	10335
Benzene	0.0142	<i>d</i>	+8634	+9431
	0.0150	<i>l</i>	-8788	-9535
		Mean	8711	9483
Chloroform	0.0149	<i>d</i>	+8074	+8837
	0.0152	<i>l</i>	-8215	-8812
		Mean	8145	8825

Hg_{green} line could not be read through these solutions.

TABLE V.

pp'-Diphenylamine bisiminocamphor.

Solvent.	Concentration: g./100 c.c.	Dextro, laevo or mean.	[M]		
			Na _D	Hg _{yel.}	Hg _{gr.}
Ethyl alcohol	0.0148	<i>d</i>	+13380*	+14030*	+19050*
	0.0151	<i>l</i>	-13080	-13990	-19010
		Mean	13230	13990	19030
Pyridine	0.0150	<i>d</i>	+13200	+13860	+18810
	0.0151	<i>l</i>	-13110	-13770	-18690
		Mean	13155	13815	18760
Acetone	0.0154	<i>d</i>	+13020	+13660	+18640
	0.0155	<i>l</i>	-12770	-13570	-18490
		Mean	12995	13615	18565
Benzene	0.0150	<i>d</i>	+12530	+13200	+18150
	0.0155	<i>l</i>	-12390	-13090	-18040
		Mean	12410	13145	18095
Methyl alcohol	0.0147	<i>d</i>	+12480	+13130	+18020
	0.0148	<i>l</i>	-12540	-13210	-18060
		Mean	12500	13170	18040
Chloroform	0.0149	<i>d</i>	+11790	+12510	+17270
	0.0148	<i>l</i>	-11690	-12370	-17120
		Mean	11740	12440	17195

TABLE VI.

Acetyl Derivative of pp'-Diphenylaminebisiminocamphor.

<i>Chloroform.</i>	$[\alpha] = \frac{168.9}{\lambda^2 - 0.1292}$;	$[M] = 5.87[\alpha]$;	$\lambda_0 = 0.8594.$	
	Concentration : g./100 c.c.	[M]		
		Na _D	Hg _{yel.}	Hg _{gr.}
Dextro	0.0912	+ 4181°	+ 4393°	+ 5357°
Leavo	0.0901	- 4172	- 4351	- 5364
Mean (obs.)	...	4176.5	4372	5360.5
Calc.	...	4143	4411	5348
Diff.	...	+ 33.5	- 39.0	+ 12.5
<i>Ethyl alcohol.</i>	$[\alpha] = \frac{151.4}{\lambda^2 - 0.1224}$;	$[M] = 5.87[\alpha]$;	$\lambda_0 = 0.8499.$	
Dextro	0.0910	+ 3629°	+ 3806°	+ 4633°
Laevo	0.0904	- 3666	- 3815	- 4650
Mean (obs.)	...	3647.5	3810.5	4641.5
Calc.	...	3615	3841	4624
Diff.	...	+ 32.5	- 30.5	+ 17.5
<i>Methyl alcohol.</i>	$[\alpha] = \frac{185.9}{\lambda^2 - 0.1347}$;	$[M] = 5.87[\alpha]$;	$\lambda_0 = 0.8670.$	
Dextro	0.0917	+ 3456	+ 3631	+ 4450
Laevo	0.0900	- 3431	- 3630	- 4445
Mean (obs.)	...	3443.5	3620.5	4447.5
Calc.	...	3418	3643	4443
Diff.	...	+ 25.5	- 22.5	+ 4.5

TABLE VI—*contd.**Acetyl Derivative of pp'-Diphenylaminebisiminocampher.*

Acetone. $[\alpha] = \frac{151.6}{\lambda^2 - 0.1843}$; $[M] = 5.37 [\alpha]$; $\lambda_0 = 0.3664$.

	Concentration: g./100 c. c.	[M]		
		N_{aD}	Hg _{yel.}	Hg _{gr.}
Dextro	0.0919	+ 3856°	+ 4060°	+ 4906°
Laevo	0.0902	- 3807	- 4048	- 5000
Mean (obs.)	...	3831.5	4054	4933
Calc.	...	3820	4072	4936
Diff.	...	+ 11.5	- 18	+ 17

Benzene. $[\alpha] = \frac{176.0}{\lambda^2 - 0.1863}$; $[M] = 5.37 [\alpha]$; $\lambda_0 = 0.3692$.

Dextro	0.0905	+ 4540°	+ 4777°	+ 5877°
Laevo	0.0895	- 4500	- 4741	- 5851
Mean (obs.)	...	4520	4759	5864
Calc.	...	4481	4779	5887
Diff.	...	+ 39.0	- 20.0	+ 27.0

Pyridine. $[\alpha] = \frac{177.3}{\lambda^2 - 0.1854}$; $[M] = 5.37 [\alpha]$; $\lambda_0 = 0.3680$.

Dextro	0.0912	+ 4560	+ 4770	+ 5887
Laevo	0.0898	- 4515	- 4726	- 5860
Mean (obs.)	...	4527.5	4748	5873.5
Calc.	...	4494	4798	5853
Diff.	...	+ 43.5	- 45.0	+ 20.5

TABLE VII.

p-Iminocamphordiphenylamine.

Solvent.	Concentration- g./100 c.c.	Dextro, laevo, or mean.	[M]		
			Na _D	Hg _{yel}	Hg _{gr.}
Ethyl alcohol	0·0306	<i>d</i>	+7107*	+7439*	+9275*
	0·0296	<i>l</i>	-7011	-7347	-9261
		Mean	7059	7388	9263
Pyridine	0·0301	<i>d</i>	+6728	+7000	+8813
	0·0308	<i>l</i>	-8736	-7006	-8837
		Mean	6731	7003	8827
Methyl alcohol	0·0303	<i>d</i>	+6303	+6513	+8236
	0·0306	<i>l</i>	-6237	-6454	-8189
		Mean	6270	6486	8213
Chloroform	0·0310	<i>d</i>	+5624	+5836	+7393
	0·0305	<i>l</i>	-5550	-5768	-7401
		Mean	5587	5802	7397
Acetone	0·0300	<i>d</i>	+5534	+5699	+7249
	0·0300	<i>l</i>	-5478	-5643	-7194
		Mean	5506	5671	7222
Benzene	0·0305	<i>d</i>	+5334	+5498	+7023
	0·0308	<i>l</i>	-5282	-5444	-6950
		Mean	5308	5471	6986

TABLE VIII.

Acetyl Derivative of p-Iminocamphordiphenylamine.

Benzene	0·1428	<i>d</i>	+2371*	+2462*	+3130*
	0·1400	<i>l</i>	-2364	-2471	-3152
		Mean	2368	2467	3141
Pyridine	0·1392	<i>d</i>	+2325	+2405	+3064
	0·1368	<i>l</i>	-2324	-2420	-3063
		Mean	2325	2413	3067
Chloroform	0·1424	<i>d</i>	+2220	+2301	+2929
	0·1444	<i>l</i>	-2202	-2293	-2900
		Mean	2211	2297	2915
Ethyl alcohol	0·1440	<i>d</i>	+2026	+2103	+2663
	0·1436	<i>l</i>	-2006	-2085	-2657
		Mean	2016	2094	2660
Acetone	0·1384	<i>d</i>	+2013	+2094	+2662
	0·1424	<i>l</i>	-1998	-2074	-2626
		Mean	2005	2064	2644
Methyl alcohol	0·1420	<i>d</i>	+1863	+1949	+2450
	0·1432	<i>l</i>	-1855	-1933	-2439
		Mean	1869	1941	2445

TABLE IX.

p-Aminocamphordiphenylamine.

Chloroform. $[\alpha] = \frac{18.98}{\lambda^2 - 0.0822}$; $[M] = 3.34 [\alpha]$; $\lambda_0 = 0.2667$.

	Concentration : g./100 c.c.	[M]			
		N_{D}	$H_{\text{g.yel.}}$	$H_{\text{g.gr.}}$	$H_{\text{g.vio.}}$
Dextro ...	0.4068	+242.5°	+254.6°	+291.5°	+595.1°
Laevo ...	0.4024	-236.4	-253.1	-290.2	-585.1
Mean (obs.)	239.45	253.8	290.8	590.1
Calc.	239.1	251.6	293.5	588.4
Diff.	+0.35	+2.2	-2.7	+1.7

Acetone. $[\alpha] = \frac{16.54}{\lambda^2 - 0.0914}$; $[M] = 3.34 [\alpha]$; $\lambda_0 = 0.3023$.

Dextro ...	0.4100	+215.9°	+232.1°	+264.7°	+566.1°
Laevo ...	0.4068	-209.3	-229.9	-262.6	-549.5
Mean (obs.)	212.6	231.0	268.55	558.8
Calc.	215.9	227.6	267.1	559.8
Diff.	-3.3	+3.4	-3.45	-1.0

Pyridine. $[\alpha] = \frac{10.86}{\lambda^2 - 0.086}$; $[M] = 3.34 [\alpha]$; $\lambda_0 = 0.2915$.

Dextro ...	0.4024	+137.0°	+145.3°	+170.1°	+340.2°
Laevo ...	0.4060	-135.7	-147.9	-172.8	-349.7
Mean (obs.)	136.35	146.6	171.45	344.9
Calc.	138.2	145.5	170.0	345.6
Diff.	-1.85	+1.1	+1.45	-0.7

Methyl alcohol. $[\alpha] = \frac{14.28}{\lambda^2 - 0.0822}$; $[M] = 3.34 [\alpha]$; $\lambda_0 = 0.2667$.

Dextro ...	0.4080	+182.8°	+195.2°	+220.2°	+440.2°
Laevo ...	0.4032	-174.0	-190.5	-215.4	-455.6
Mean (obs.)	178.4	192.9	217.8	447.9
Calc.	179.9	189.3	220.7	442.9
Diff.	-1.5	+3.6	-2.9	+5.0

Ethyl alcohol. $[\alpha] = \frac{15.94}{\lambda^2 - 0.0799}$; $[M] = 3.34 [\alpha]$; $\lambda_0 = 0.2827$.

Dextro ...	0.3988	+200.9°	+213.5°	+242.9°	+502.4°
Laevo ...	0.4008	-195.8	-212.5	-237.5	-484.3
Mean (obs.)	198.35	213.0	240.2	484.35
Calc.	199.0	209.5	243.7	484.3
Diff.	-0.65	+3.5	-3.5	+9.05

Benzene. $[\alpha] = \frac{19.34}{\lambda^2 - 0.0892}$; $[M] = 3.34 [\alpha]$; $\lambda_0 = 0.2937$.

Dextro ...	0.4088	+253.3°	+269.6°	+306.4°	+661.8°
Laevo ...	0.4056	-247.4	-263.5	-305.4	-650.6
Mean (obs.)	250.35	266.55	305.9	656.2
Calc.	250.2	263.8	308.9	641.8
Diff.	+0.15	+2.75	-3.0	+14.4

TABLE X.

Diacyl Derivative of p-Aminooamphordiphenylamine.

Chloroform. $[\alpha] = \frac{16.81}{\lambda^2 - 0.0761}$; $[M] = 4.18[\alpha]$; $\lambda_0 = 0.2759$.

	Concentration : g./100 c.c.	[M]			
		N_{D_D}	$Hg_{yal.}$	$Hg_{gr.}$	$Hg_{vio.}$
Dextro ...	0.5000	+263.8°	+275.8°	+317.7°	+614.5°
Laevo ...	0.5020	-258.1	-274.8	-316.4	-608.0
Mean (obs.)	260.7	275.3	317.05	611.25
Calc.	259.6	272.9	316.8	614.9
Diff.	+1.1	+2.4	+0.25	-3.65

Benzene. $[\alpha] = \frac{17.33}{\lambda^2 - 0.0913}$; $[M] = 4.18[\alpha]$; $\lambda_0 = 0.3023$.

Dextro ...	0.5020	+263.1°	+304.0°	+345.5°	+741.0°
Laevo ...	0.4996	-264.4	-301.2	-344.0	-736.2
Mean (obs.)	263.7	302.6	344.8	738.6
Calc.	263.0	298.4	350.0	734.7
Diff.	+0.7	+4.2	-5.2	+3.9

Acetone. $[\alpha] = \frac{15.42}{\lambda^2 - 0.0621}$; $[M] = 4.18[\alpha]$; $\lambda_0 = 0.2365$.

Dextro ...	0.5040	+244.6°	+257.1°	+298.5°	+597.1°
Laevo ...	0.5004	-242.3	-259.0	-296.6	-593.2
Mean (obs.)	243.45	256.05	297.55	595.15
Calc.	243.1	255.8	298.4	598.1
Diff.	+0.35	+2.25	-0.85	-2.95

Pyridine.

Dextro ...	0.5020	+124.9°	+137.4°	+166.5°	+337.3°
Laevo ...	0.5012	-125.1	-133.5	-162.7	-329.5
Mean	125.0	135.45	164.6	334.4

Rotations in the alcohols (ethyl and methyl) were not determined as the solubility in them was too small to determine the angle of rotation accurately.

TABLE XI.

pp'-Diphenylmethanebisiminocamphor.

Solvent.	Concentration : g./100 c.c.	Dextro laevo or mean.	[M]		
			Na _D	Hg _{yel.}	Hg _{gr.}
Pyridine	0.1248	<i>d</i>	+4552°	+4749°	+6016°
	0.1294	<i>l</i>	-4508	-4722	-6012
		Mean	4520	4736	6014
Benzene	0.1204	<i>d</i>	+4471	+4658.0	+5947
	0.1208	<i>l</i>	-4458	-4661	-5928
		Mean	4465	4660	5938
Chloroform	0.1240	<i>d</i>	+4442	+4620	+5878
	0.1204	<i>l</i>	-4410	-4615	-5846
		Mean	4426	4618	5860
Ethyl alcohol	0.1228	<i>d</i>	+4108	+4263	+5389
	0.1220	<i>l</i>	-4049	-4232	-5364
		Mean	4026	4248	5377

Acetone. $[\alpha] = \frac{157.8}{\lambda^2 - 0.1499}$; $[M] = 4.94[\alpha]$; $\lambda_0 = 0.8871$.

Dextro	0.1196	+4005°	+4193°	+5285°
Laevo	0.1200	-3973	-4190	-5269
Mean (obs.)	...	3989	4196	5277
Calc.	...	3950	4284	5265
Diff.	...	+39	-38	+22

Methyl alcohol. $[\alpha] = \frac{161.6}{\lambda^2 - 0.1440}$; $[M] = 4.94[\alpha]$; $\lambda_0 = 0.8795$.

Dextro	0.1244	+3990°	+4169°	+5220°
Laevo	0.1216	-3941	-4149	-5196
Mean (obs.)	...	3966	4156	5208
Calc.	...	3928	4201	5177
Diff.	...	+38	-45	+31

TABLE XII.

pp'-Diphenylmethanebisaminocamphor.

Solvent.	Concentration : g./100 c.c.	Dextro. laevo or mean.	[M]		
			N_D	$H_{g_{yel.}}$	$H_{g_{gr.}}$
Benzene	0.4048	<i>d</i>	+486.0°	+529.0°	+602.9°
	0.3968	<i>l</i>	-493.2	-540.7	-605.6
		Mean	489.6	529.9	604.3
Chloroform	0.4086	<i>d</i>	+487.4	+530.3	+599.6
	0.4004	<i>l</i>	-485.1	-528.3	-591.3
		Mean	486.25	529.3	591.9
Pyridine	0.4040	<i>d</i>	+252.7	+283.5	+320.5
	0.4020	<i>l</i>	-247.8	-278.7	-315.9
		Mean	250.25	281.6	318.2
<i>Methyl alcohol.</i> $[\alpha] = \frac{17.66}{\lambda^2 - 0.0996}$; $[M] = 4.98[\alpha]$; $\lambda_0 = 0.3159$.					
Dextro	0.1980*		+352.2°	+377.3°	+440.1°
Laevo	0.1904*		-353.1	-379.2	-444.6
Mean (obs.)	...		352.7	378.25	442.85
Calc.	...		355.4	376.4	443.5
Diff.	...		-2.7	+2.85	-1.15
<i>Acetone.</i> $[\alpha] = \frac{26.53}{\lambda^2 - 0.0655}$; $[M] = 4.98[\alpha]$; $\lambda_0 = 0.2559$.					
Dextro	0.4000		+466.8°	+498.0°	+566.3°
Laevo	0.4048		-464.3	-502.0	-572.3
Mean (obs.)	...		465.55	500.0	569.3
Calc.	...		468.2	491.8	567.6
Diff.	...		-2.65	+8.2	-1.7

* The solubility of the substance in methyl alcohol was found to be very small; hence half the usual concentration was employed in these experiments.

TABLE XII—*continued*.

Ethyl alcohol. $[\alpha] = \frac{23 \cdot 10}{\lambda^2 - 0 \cdot 0573}$; $[M] = 4 \cdot 98[\alpha]$; $\lambda_0 = 0 \cdot 2394$.

	Concentration : g./100 c.c.	[M]		
		Na _D	Hg _{yel.}	Hg _{gr.}
Dextro ...	0.4020	+396.4°	+427.3°	+476.8°
Laevo ...	0.3968	-399.0	-420.5	-476.8
Mean (obs.)	392.7	423.9	476.8
Calc.	396.6	415.9	477.2
Diff.	-3.9	+8.0	-0.4

Further work on similar lines is in progress.

We wish to make grateful acknowledgement to the Government of Bihar and Orissa, in the Ministry of Education, for the grant of a research scholarship to one of us (B.B.) which has enabled him to take part in this investigation. We also wish to acknowledge the valuable assistance which we received from Babu Indramani Mahanti, B.Sc., the Head Assistant of the Chemical Department.

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Received March 11, 1930.